

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Impact Lab

ESiIL Innovation Summit 2025 Evaluation Report

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Introduction

Program Description

The Environmental Data Science Innovation & Impact Lab (ESIIL) is a next-generation NSF data synthesis center that enables a global community of environmental data scientists to leverage emerging analytics to develop science-based solutions to pressing environmental challenges. These activities support ESIIL's mission to *"Empower a broad community to accelerate open environmental data science (EDS)"* (www.esiil.org).

This report summarizes the evaluation of the third annual ESIIL Environmental Data Science Innovation Summit, which took place on September 23rd – 25th, 2025 in Boulder, CO. The event brought together 110 Earth and Environmental Data Scientists from a variety of disciplines to build and strengthen the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. The Summit theme was "Environmental Tipping Points and Transformation." It followed an "unconference" meeting format (Budd et al., 2015) that encouraged participant engagement and involvement in shaping the Summit and feedback each day to inform what was included in subsequent days of the meeting. The overarching goals of the 2025 Summit were:

- **Explore big data to understand environmental tipping points and transformations** by identifying data synthesis opportunities and utilizing ESIIL cloud-compute capabilities.
- **Promote best practices in ethical, open science** by supporting accessibility and usability of environmental data by all stakeholders.
- **Champion ethical practices** in environmental science, and encourage the responsible use of AI.
- **Support teams** by establishing collaborations around data-inspired themes across different disciplines, sectors, and career stages.

Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation team used a collaborative approach (King and Stevahn 2013, Shulha et al. 2016) to develop the Summit evaluation activities with the project leadership and used feedback from prior annual Summits to revise evaluation surveys. An online Pre-Summit survey was sent to all registered attendees before the Summit began. On the final day of the Summit, attendees were invited to take an online reflection survey to share their experiences at the Summit.

ESIIL Program evaluation is co-led by Anne U. Gold, Megan K. Littrell, Emily Ward, and Abby McConnell. This study has been approved by the University of Colorado Institutional Research Board (IRB) Protocol 23-0162. Funding for this work was provided by the National Science Foundation (NSF, Award #DBI-2153040). Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the NSF.

Executive Summary

Pre-Summit Training Opportunities

92% of reflection survey respondents **engaged in the Pre-Summit activities**. A consistent majority of respondents **agreed or strongly agreed** that these activities **prepared them for the Summit**, with the strongest agreement for **CyVerse and GitHub training (80%)** and the “Science Jam” **Brainstorming** session (54%).

Snapshot of 2025 Summit Experience and Outcomes

98% Of respondents were very (84%) or moderately (14%) **satisfied overall** with the Summit.

97% Agreed or strongly agreed that the Summit **atmosphere** was **relaxed, open, friendly** and **fun**.

95% Agreed or strongly agreed that the **unconference format** worked well.

91% Agreed or strongly agreed that they **felt respected** by their colleagues.

86% Agreed or strongly agreed that they learned about **new technologies or techniques** applicable to their research and that **AI Tools were useful** for their work at the Summit.

84% indicated that they **plan to continue using AI/ML** in their work after the Summit.

Impressions of group dynamics and AI use were mixed: 39% of respondents **disagreed** that the use of **AI tools increased tension in their working group**, **33%** **neither** agreed nor disagreed, and **28%** **agreed**.

77% were **motivated to continue to work on EDS ideas** after the Summit to a large or very large extent.

Belonging and Identity in EDS: Respondents saw a statistically significant **greater overlap between themselves and the EDS community at the end of the Summit** than before it ($Z = 4.29, p < 0.001$).

Respondents rated the breakout groups the highest of the Summit activities, noting that the breakouts convened enthusiastic collaborators and resulted in effective brainstorming and project planning that could carry on past the Summit. Respondents suggested improvements including more intentionality and time to form and work in the groups, additional structure and support for groups to improve productivity, and accessibility of materials prior to the Summit.

Respondents' Reflections on the Best Parts of the 2025 ESIL Innovation Summit

Key Themes	Highlights
Networking and Community Building	Respondents valued meeting new people, connecting with like-minded individuals, and expanding their professional networks.
Teamwork and Collaboration	Working on brainstorming ideas and engaging in live collaboration on meaningful projects was highly appreciated for fostering effective teamwork.
Welcoming and Supportive Environment	Many highlighted the welcoming atmosphere, inclusivity, and strong support from organizers as key strengths of the Summit
Technical Learning and Resources	Respondents valued access to technical discussions, tools, and resources that supported their projects.
Exposure to Multiple Perspectives	Respondents appreciated hearing ideas from people with different backgrounds, including indigenous perspectives and interdisciplinary approaches.

Respondents' Recommendations for Improving Future ESIL Innovation Summits

Key Themes	Examples and Recommended Improvements
Advance Communication and Preparation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early Information Sharing: Respondents suggested <i>"letting participants know potential science questions one day in advance"</i> to give attendees <i>"time to process what they may be interested in."</i> • Pre-Summit Group Formation: Several recommended forming groups earlier to prior to the Summit to allow attendees the <i>"opportunity to start pulling together data earlier."</i>
Group Dynamics and Selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving Group Dynamics: Some noted that <i>"it's a little tough for those that have quieter voices to have a chance for input"</i> or that group work was inefficient due to those who wish not to <i>"steamroll the conversation."</i> • Clearer Processes: Respondents felt the topic selection process was <i>"a bit chaotic"</i> and that it was <i>"it was hard to tell how many people were actually interested in a topic since we shifted posters every few minutes."</i> Some also noted that they wished there was <i>"more flexibility around joining groups."</i> • Inter-group Engagement: Respondents suggested that it would be great to engage with other teams since they didn't <i>"get to interact much"</i> with those on other teams.
Time Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration Concerns: Suggestions included indicating that the <i>"last day could be extended to the afternoon."</i> One respondent suggested that <i>"a second science jam where the goal is to link data to the questions/topics"</i> could be a way to incorporate more time. • Balance Between Activities: Respondents indicated they wanted more networking opportunities without compromising project time. Some noted that it was <i>"exhausting being in the room for an entire day"</i> and then <i>"asked to go for socials that evening."</i>
Expectations and Scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realistic Goals: Respondents noted that project expectations <i>"were too big"</i> within <i>"such a short time scale,"</i> and that the <i>"Summit could have helped bound the expectations better."</i>

Key Themes	Examples and Recommended Improvements
Group Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical and Focused Work Sessions: Respondents indicated that they wanted “<i>more technical training</i>” and “<i>breakouts for groups once they are going in a solid direction.</i>” Others mentioned “<i>more hands-on with data analysis and digging into relevant datasets for insights.</i>” • Increased Collaboration Time: Some respondents expressed that the facilitation was “<i>a bit heavy handed</i>” and that it “<i>disrupted the flow of working with teams.</i>” They suggested that they wished more time was spent “<i>connecting with the other participants.</i>” • Demonstrations: Respondents suggested that “<i>mini-sessions of working group awardees</i>” can help to demonstrate the “<i>commitment they needed to produce in order to success as a working group</i>” that resulted in meaningful advancement from participating in the Summit.

Respondents’ Main Take-Aways from the 2025 ESIL Innovation Summit

Key Themes	Highlights
Skill Development in Cyberinfrastructure and AI Tools	Respondents gained hands-on experience with platforms like CyVerse, GitHub, and cloud computing, as well as practical knowledge of AI-assisted coding and metadata management. Respondents noted that these skills are helping them build secure, scalable workflows and better understand data structures and interoperability challenges.
New Collaborations and Interdisciplinary Networks	Respondents frequently mentioned forming new collaborations and connecting with experts across disciplines, including RAD management, simulation modeling, and Indigenous knowledge systems. These relationships are expected to foster future research partnerships and enrich their scientific perspectives.
Community Building	Many respondents expressed appreciation for the welcoming and respectful environment of the Summit. This atmosphere fostered a sense of belonging and purpose.
Resources and Tools for Research	Many respondents appreciated access to advanced tools, such as CyVerse and cloud computing facilities, that enhanced their research capabilities. Respondents also discovered new templates, data libraries, that are helping them to structure their projects more effectively and access tools that support long-term data archiving and collaborative research.
Improved Data Science and Analytical Methods	Respondents reported learning new analytical techniques such as geospatial analysis in R, that are enhancing their ability to work with complex datasets and apply rigorous methods to environmental questions.
Personal and Professional Growth	Many attendees reflected on increased confidence in their scientific identity, improved ability to manage difficult situations, and a clearer vision of the kind of researcher they aspire to be.

¹ Icons in the Executive Summary provided by the Noun Project’s creators: Iconathon, Imam, Izwar Muis, Sitaesmi, Studio 365, Robert Chiaver, Thomas Le Bas, and Zuri.

Summit Attendee Characteristics

Summit and Survey Participation

There were 110 attendees at the 2025 ESIL Innovation Summit. The pre- and post-Summit surveys were sent to 98 people who attended the Summit as participants or as breakout group facilitators. 52 of these attendees responded to the Summit pre-survey (53% response rate) and 38 responded to the post Summit reflection survey (39% response rate). Aggregated participant responses to survey items are shared throughout the report through description, visual representations, and statistical analyses as appropriate for pre- and post-event comparisons. Please note that percentages of each response on survey items in this report are rounded to the nearest whole number and may not always add up to 100% due to rounding or due to allowance of multiple selections.

Respondent Demographic Information

Ninety-six percent of respondents reported that they live in the U.S. representing 19 U.S. States (Figure 1), and 4% reported that they live outside of the U.S. representing two other countries (Canada and Pakistan).

Figure 1

Bubble map of 2025 Summit survey respondents

Note. Blue areas represent a higher concentration of survey respondents.

50% percent of survey respondents identified as female, and 33% identified as male. The majority of respondents identified as White, Caucasian, European, or European American (59%). Respondents also identified as Asian or Asian American (14%); Black, African American, or African (8%); American Indian or Alaska Native (6%); or Hispanic, Latinx, or Hispanic or Latinx American (6%). Four percent of respondents preferred not to answer, 7% selected more than one category, and 2% included a written response describing their race or ethnicity (Table 1).

59%	White, Caucasian, European, or European American
14%	Asian or Asian American
8%	Black, African American, or African
6%	American Indian or Alaska Native
6%	Hispanic, Latinx; Hispanic or Latinx American
4%	I prefer not to answer
0%	Middle Eastern or North African; Middle Eastern or North African American
2%	Not listed (<i>please specify</i>)
7%	More than one selection

Note. “More than one selection” and “Not listed” are not included in the total percentage because they both include multiple responses selected.

Education, Career Experience, and Affiliation

Just over half of respondents (52%) had earned a **Doctoral degree**, 28% held **Master’s degrees**, and 15% had completed some graduate work. Two percent of respondents had earned a Bachelor’s degree, 2% had earned an Associate degree, and 0% preferred not to answer (Table 2).

52%	Doctoral degree
28%	Master’s degree
15%	Some graduate work
2%	Bachelor’s degree
2%	Associate degree
0%	I prefer not to answer

Figure 2

Career Stage: Thirty percent of respondents were **students**, and just under a third of respondents (30%) described themselves as **Early Career** (0 – 5 years of professional experience or post-doctoral fellow). Twenty-eight percent were Mid-Career (6 – 15 years of professional experience). Another 9% were at a Senior stage in their career (more than 15 years of experience), and 2% reported “Other” (Figure 2).

Field of Study: Survey respondents were also asked to indicate the field in which they received their highest degree. These degrees encompassed a **range of academic disciplines**, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of Environmental Data Science (EDS), with individuals from a wide array of fields contributing to its advancement and application (Table 3).

Table 3

Natural Sciences	Engineering and Applied Sciences	Social Sciences and Humanities	Interdisciplinary & Miscellaneous
Biology	Computer Science	Anthropology	Public Health
Ecology	Aerospace Engineering	Environmental Data Science	Biostatistics
Geology	Applied Geophysics	Business Administration	
Wildlife and Fisheries Biology	Civil Engineering	Natural Science Education	
Evolutionary Biology	Network Science	International Development	
Geoscience	Biological Engineering	Political Science	
Evolution and Conservation Biology	Mathematics	Sustainability Management	
Forestry and Natural Resources			
Population Biology			
Earth and Climate Science			
Aquatic and Fishery Science			
Integrative Biology			
Evolutionary Genomics			
Natural Resources			

Affiliation: Almost three-fourths of respondents work at an **Academic (higher education) institution (64%)**, followed by other non-profit organizations (7%), Federal Government agencies (5%), Tribal organizations (5%), Research and Development Non-profit organizations (3%), Private For-profit organizations (3%), State Government agencies (2%), Local Government agencies (2%), Industry (2%), K-12 or informal education (2%), and Self-employed (2%). Three percent of respondents chose “Other” and reported being in retirement or employment with international organizations.

Academic Affiliations Represented. Of those respondents working at academic institutions, the majority reported affiliation with a **Research-Intensive institution (59%)**. Fifteen percent of academic affiliations included institutions serving both undergraduate and graduate students, 10% were Hispanic-serving institutions, and 8% were minority-serving institutions. Some respondents also reported affiliation with a primarily undergraduate serving institution (2%), a professional program (2%), a American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institution (2%), and a Historically Black University (2%) (Table 4).

Table 4

Survey Respondent Academic Affiliations	
59%	Research Intensive
15%	Undergraduate & Graduate student serving
2%	Primarily Undergraduate student serving
10%	Hispanic-Serving Institution
8%	Minority-Serving Institution
2%	Professional Program
2%	American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institution
2%	Historically Black University

Note. The sum of percentages exceeds 100% because respondents could select more than one response.

Primary role in the Environmental Data Science (EDS) Field: Survey respondents were asked to choose their primary roles in the broad field of EDS. **Researchers (41%) represented the largest group at the Summit** with smaller percentages of people who primarily identified as a Student (30%), Director or Program Manager (9%), Project/Field Manager (9%), Educator (2%), and Analyst (2%). Seven percent of participants selected “Other” (Figure 3).

Figure 3

Note. “Other” roles specified by respondents included “engineer creating open source software products,” “product manager working as a technician,” “community manager,” “educator,” and “retired active researcher.”

Disciplinary fields in EDS: The most commonly selected EDS fields selected by respondents included **Environmental Science (29%), Biological Science (20%), and Computer/Data Science (12%)**. Fewer respondents represented Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (9%), Geoscience (9%), Social Science (8%), Economics (3%), Engineering (2%), and Math (2%). The majority of respondents selected more than one response as their main field in EDS. Three percent of respondents indicated that they do not work in the EDS field. Open-ended “Other” responses (4%) included: Indigenous Studies, Ecology, Marine Science, Information Design, and Public Health.

Professional Society Memberships: The list of memberships comprises a **wide range of professional societies**, including those related to natural sciences, social sciences, mathematics, ecology, geophysics, biology, geography, and more. Some societies are discipline-specific (e.g., Society of Ecological Restoration, Ecological Society of America), while others are more broadly focused on fields like geophysics, earth sciences, and data science. Additionally, there are some societies dedicated to supporting underrepresented groups (e.g., Women in Machine Learning, Society for the Advancement of Chicanos/Hispanics and Native Americans in Science) and promoting diversity in STEM. Several societies (e.g., American Geophysical Union and the Ecological Society of America) appeared multiple times in the list, indicating their prominence and potential popularity among professionals.

Accommodation Requests

On the pre-survey, respondents were asked to describe any accommodations needs they have in order to participate optimally in virtual and in-person ESIIIL events (including the Summit). Five attendees provided responses to this question. Exact responses are provided below with any potentially identifying information redacted:

- *No accommodations needed, but a gluten free snack option for in person would be cool. (Though I usually plan ahead and bring my own)*
- *I am colorblind but no accommodation needed.*
- *recorded events are tremendously helpful. [redacted/potentially identifying details] so it is helpful to be able to catch up on things that I cannot make.*
- *Moved pretty quickly on getting in the cloud, so a slow version of getting aligned on cyverse, etc.*
- *I do not require specific accommodations at this time. However, I would highly value clear communication of schedules in advance, reliable internet connectivity support for virtual sessions, and accessible formats of shared materials (e.g., recordings or slides). These would ensure I can participate optimally in both virtual and in-person events, especially given my international commitments and travel*

Pre-Summit Participation and Summit Goals

Participation in Pre-Summit Activities

Prior to the Summit, the leadership team engaged Summit attendees in optional Pre-Summit engagement and training sessions. Sessions provided an opportunity to brainstorm research topics and training in cloud computing with artificial intelligence, Cyverse and Github, and research team leadership.

92% of Summit reflection survey respondents reported engaging in the Pre-Summit activities:

- **27%** participated in “Science Jam: Creative Brainstorming to Inspire Innovation” (August 5th, 2025)
- **32%** participated in “Navigating CyVerse and Github: A Gateway for Advance Computation for Science” (September 3rd, 2025)
- **23%** participated in “Creative Data Exploration in the Cloud with AI: Innovating with Open Science” (September 9th, 2025)
- **11%** participating in “Leadership Training” (September 22nd, 2025)

On the Summit reflection survey, respondents were also asked to rate how useful each training was and how well the technical trainings prepared them for the Summit. Across the board, most respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the training components they participated in helped prepare them for the Summit. Of these, respondents tended to agree or strongly agree most frequently that **the Navigating CyVerse and Github, “Science Jam” Brainstorming, and Cloud Computing Basics** trainings helped prepare for the Summit (Figure 4).

Figure 4

Note. Respondents selected N/A if they did not participate in a pre-training activity.

Respondents' Personal Summit Goals

The Summit pre-survey asked respondents to share 1-3 personal goals for the Summit. Common themes in their responses are summarized below.

- **Networking and Collaboration:** The most common theme among respondents was the desire to network, connect, and collaborate with others. Many respondents emphasized the importance of connecting with peers, researchers, and professionals. Goals include building professional networks, forming collaborations for future projects, and joining working groups that extend beyond the Summit.
- **Learning and Skill Development:** Respondents were eager to gain new knowledge and technical skills. Participants wanted to learn about environmental data analysis tools, open science principles, risk assessment, and innovative methodologies. Several mentioned improving their understanding of databases, cloud-based computing, and data-driven decision-making.
- **Open Science and Data Sharing:** Respondents expressed interest in learning how to share data effectively, use open-source tools, and contribute to open science initiatives. This included understanding data management tools that encourage findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable data; improving data accessibility; and collaborating on shared resources.
- **Applying Knowledge to Real-World Challenges:** Many participants aimed to apply their learning to address environmental and societal issues such as climate change, hazard risk mitigation, and sustainability. They wanted to translate Summit insights into actionable strategies for their research or community projects.
- **Interdisciplinary Engagement:** Several responses highlight the desire to engage in interdisciplinary research—combining ecology, data science, social sciences, and policy. This included learning how different fields approach environmental challenges and fostering cross-sector collaboration.
- **Professional Growth and Career Development:** Some participants viewed the Summit as an opportunity to advance their careers by gaining exposure to new ideas, showcasing their work, and identifying potential mentors or collaborators.

Respondents' Recommendation for Improving Pre-Summit Trainings

Themes that arose from respondents' recommendations for improving the Pre-Summit trainings and exemplary quotes are provided below.

Provide Flexible Learning Options

- Respondents suggested offering asynchronous tutorials for technical sessions to allow participants to learn at their own pace and more synchronous lessons to accommodate schedules.
 - *"Asynchronous tutorial would work better for me than keeping up or playing along in a live session."*
 - *"I just wish there were a few more opportunities for synchronous sessions since I have a heavy teaching load this semester and had to miss several."*

- Make recordings and links available early so participants can review and identify potential barriers before sessions.
 - *“As ESILL now has recordings of those pre- trainings, specifically the technical ones, it is best to send them early on to watch whoever would like and then go over together so that they might’ve already discovered potential barriers we can help.”*
 - *“The breakout rooms were great along with the ability to move around rooms. The links to the working docs should be made available earlier in session.”*

Enhance Interaction and Idea Sharing

- Provide more time for participants to meet and network before the Summit.
 - *“More time for participants to meet each other. This was the hardest part about finding a group at the summit.”*
- Share topics and working documents earlier to allow participants to prepare ideas for collaboration.
 - *“Science Jam Brainstorm was great to get ideas flowing but I wish that the topics had been shared with us ahead of time so we had a little bit more time to think through our ideas we might want to contribute during the 3 breakout sessions during the jam.”*
- Ensure that there is equitable engagement.
 - *“I feel that the jam could be improved to make sure all voices are weighted similarly.”*

Expand and Specialize Training Content

- Offer additional sessions on advanced tools and skills.
 - *“Maybe more CyVerse/Docker/GitHub type training.”*
- Consider splitting technical topics across multiple days for better comprehension.
 - *“Multiple days for Science Jam, maybe split the topics across different days/hours.”*
 - *“Extending to one more day is very difficult and expensive to do, but I believe the forward momentum of each project might be significantly deeper with another deep workday.”*

Improve Instructions and Avenues for Support

- Provide clear, simplified instructions and step-by-step outlines.
 - *“Even though there were instructions for the tech session, they were hard to follow, even with support. Perhaps a simplified outline of the steps in addition to the already available detailed one?”*
- Create a pre-training checklist to help facilitators prepare.
 - *“For the trainings, it would be helpful to have a pre-training checklist of steps to try and a location to report issues so that facilitators may know what will come up and how to fix said issues. This could also be incorporated into a FAQ style document to keep memory of issues for future attendees and facilitators.”*

- Consider breakout rooms for participants who fall behind.
 - *“In the cloud computing trainings, a lot of folks had technical difficulties and then struggled to catch up after addressing those, so it could help to maybe have a breakout room for those feeling behind Catch up.”*

Improve Session Efficiency

- Streamline technical setup.
 - *“I think a bit of time was wasted with CyVerse setup.”*
- Clarify session purpose and timing.
 - *“I’m not exactly sure, but it was difficult to allocate time for this among lots of other commitments before the summit. Perhaps to clearly explain what each is for and who it would help and maybe if they weren’t quite so far in advance.”*

Motivate Through Examples

- Invite past participants who successfully created projects to share their experiences and inspire new attendees
 - *“Bringing some of the past workshop participants who successfully created a product as speakers would be a good motivator.”*

Summit Evaluation Outcomes

Participant Satisfaction with the ESIL Innovation Summit

Ninety-eight percent of respondents were very or moderately **satisfied** with the ESIL Innovation Summit overall (84% “Very Satisfied;” 14% “Moderately Satisfied”).

Respondents generally agreed that the various components of the Summit agenda were effective. Respondents rated **breakout group time** the most highly, with **97%** agreeing or strongly agreeing that this was an effective part of the Summit (Figure 5).

Figure 5

Evaluation of Breakout Group Work

A majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that breakout groups:

- **developed initial plans for projects (100%),**
- **were enthusiastic collaborators (95%),**
- **engaged in effective brainstorming (94%),**
- **developed plans to collaborate beyond the Summit (89%),**
- **created outlines for a project (86%),** and
- **made plans for future collaboration seemed feasible (84%)** (Figure 6).

Figure 6

Additional Feedback on Breakout Groups

Time Constraints

Some respondents indicated that they needed more time to engage with their group.

- *“Just a little more time on day 3!”*
- *“We needed more time to work in groups”*

Broader Interaction with Summit Attendees

Several respondents indicated that they wished they were able to interact with more attendees of the Summit to exchange ideas.

- *“I do wish there were other opportunities to be in small groups with people to talk about things and exchange ideas.”*
- *“The only downside of the groups is that it limited interaction with the rest of the people at the summit.”*

Structural and General Support for Groups

Several respondents indicated that better tools and clearer structure would improve group productivity and alignment with summit goals.

- *“Our breakout room didn't have a functioning whiteboard, which would have been nice.”*
- *“I think there could have been a little more structural support for working groups. Our group did a lot of conversing, discussing, and relationships building – which is great! – but I don't feel like we really aligned with the goals of the summit and the huge task we were supposedly addressing.”*

Accessibility of Relevant Materials

Respondents suggested access to materials before the Summit to prepare for breakout groups.

- *“It would have been nice to have relevant datasets identified before the summit, so each group would be able to dig into them during the breakout groups.”*

Evaluation of Artificial Intelligence Tool Use, Technical Support, and Cyberinfrastructure

Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools

Summit participants were asked to rate the **extent to which data and computing infrastructure facilitated the use of AI/ML in their working group's proposal** (Figure 7). Responses were mixed, with **25%** indicating to a **Large or Very Large Extent**, **30%** indicating to a **Small or Very Small Extent**, and **28%** indicating to a **Moderate Extent**.

Figure 7

Summit participants were asked the rate their agreement with statements about the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) tools related to the usefulness of these tools and attitudes about their use (Figure 8).

The majority of respondents **agreed or strongly agreed** that **AI tools were useful** for their Summit working group (**86%**) and that they **intend to continue using AI/ML** in their work after the Summit (**84%**).

Fifty-nine percent of respondents **agreed or strongly agreed** that they **have a more positive view of the utility of AI tools** in their work after participating in the Summit. Twenty-eight percent of respondents indicated a neutral response and **14% disagreed or strongly disagreed** that their view have become more positive.

Thirty-nine percent of respondents **disagreed or strongly disagreed** that the **use of AI tools increased tension** in their working group, with 33% indicating a neutral response and **28%** who **agreed or strongly agreed** that tension had increased.

Figure 8

Technical Support and Cyberinfrastructure

Roughly three-quarters of respondents agreed that they learned about **new technologies or techniques applicable to their research (86%)**, **gained a broader understanding of data science (86%)**, learned about **new opportunities for synthesis of data in their field (78%)**, and gained a broader understanding of **cyberinfrastructure (78%)** (Figure 9)

Figure 9

Evaluation of the Unconference Format

The Summit was designed following the common elements of an “unconference” style meeting (Budd et al., 2015). Survey items and observations of the Summit conducted by an evaluator focused on the following six broad design elements of an unconference style meeting:

- There are opportunities for participants to directly influence what is happening at the Summit (e.g., through topics, presentations, sharing of interest and expertise).
- The discussions and engagement in the breakout groups appear relevant for attendees.
- There is an emphasis on contributions from every participant and facilitation is welcoming regardless of how experienced they are (“no idea is too trivial”).
- The Summit atmosphere is relaxed, open, friendly, fun, and welcoming (e.g., for newcomers and those new to EDS).
- Participants learn about useful skills or tools related to EDS, or they applied skills and tools to EDS work.
- There are opportunities for and encouragement of collaborative work and interactive knowledge exchange/transdisciplinary work.

Reflection survey respondents provided feedback on the unconference style format (Figure 10). Highlights included:

Welcoming Atmosphere: Most survey respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the **atmosphere was relaxed and friendly (97%)** and that the Summit **welcomed contributions and ideas from all participants, regardless of background experience (95%)**.

Collaboration and Networking: Most respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the Summit offered adequate **opportunities for collaborative, transdisciplinary work and exchange of ideas (94%)**, relevant **breakout group activities (97%)**, was **welcoming for newcomers to the field (89%)**, and **networking (86%)**.

Participant Influence: The majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that there were opportunities to **directly influence what was happening each day at the Summit (67%)**.

Application of Skills or Tools: Over three-fourths of respondents agreed that they had **learned about and/or applied useful skills or tools related to EDS at the Summit (89%)**.

Figure 10

Most respondents also tended to agree or strongly agree that the **meeting was well-facilitated (97%)**, **speakers and presenters were engaging (97%)**, the **food provided was good (97%)**, the **unconference format worked well (94%)**, the **goals of the sessions were clearly communicated (94%)**, the **online resources were useful (94%)**, that there were **plenty of networking opportunities (86%)**, and **interactive communication through Slack was effective (75%)** (Figure 11).

Figure 11

Evaluator Observations of the Summit Unconference Format

Context: Two evaluation team members attended the Summit. One evaluator took notes throughout the whole-group sessions, with specific focus on activities centered around participants’ choosing their research topics and forming groups, and their reflections (group share-outs) on this process.

Locations:

- The whole-group Summit sessions took place at the University of Colorado Boulder in a large Auditorium room in the Sustainability, Energy, and Environment Community (SEEC) building. In the SEEC Auditorium, tables were set up seating 6 – 8 people each. Tables included sticky notes and pipe cleaners to support creative engagement.
- Large poster paper sheets were hung up along the walls around the room with research themes and topics and questions to consider. There were 18 topics, grouped by 8 overarching themes (These topics

and questions were generated from ideas participants shared in the pre-summit brainstorming session (Science Jam). Overarching themes & the numbered posters/topics associated with each:

- 1 Defining tipping points and transformations
- 2-4 Understanding environmental drivers
- 5 -7 Understanding social drivers
- 8-10 Detecting and Predicting tipping points
- 9-13 Understanding Environmental Impacts
- 14 Understanding social Impacts of tipping points
- 15-17 Management and adaptation strategies
- 18 Cross-cutting

Communication:

- The ESIL Team and Summit participants used Slack to communicate throughout the Summit
- Github: After participants formed their working groups, they shared progress each day using templates in Github that included prompts for what information to summarize/share and that allowed group members to share text, data, visualizations, etc.

Participatory Elements in Summit Agenda and Observation Themes: The agenda of the Summit and Pre-Summit activities included various participatory components. Pre-Summit activities included a “Science Jam,” which provided an opportunity for participants to generate ideas for research topics and questions they would like to include in the Summit, and an opportunity to explore cloud-based datasets.

An ESIL evaluator took notes during the whole-group sessions, documenting the process participants went through to identify their research topics, form working groups, and share their working group’s progress. The evaluator noted any observations that connected to a set of six themes centered on elements of the unconference format. The evaluator also noted additional prominent themes that arose, and wrote a summary of observations for each theme:

Observation Theme 1: *There are opportunities for participants to directly influence what is happening at the summit (e.g., through topics, presentations, sharing of interest and expertise).*

- On the first day of the Summit, ESIL leadership member shared that the list of 18 research topics was generated from suggestions contributed through attendees’ applications and the Pre-Summit “Science Jam” session, in which Summit participants contributed ideas for research topics. The Leadership team member indicated that although these topics were suggested, participants could be flexible in modifying the topics as they formed their working groups.
- On Day 1, participants chose an initial topic they were interested in and spent time talking with others interested in the topic. They met in front of the poster paper with the associated research topic, and the facilitators guided participants to change groups three times so that they could consider multiple topics of interest and speak to other potential working group members before choosing their group and research focus.
 - After this session, the facilitators shared observations that there were a lot of new ideas generated, including rewording/reframing one of the existing topics, adding two new topics

that fell under the “Tipping Points” general category, and adding another poster paper with a new research topic.

Observation Theme 2: *The discussions and engagement in the breakout groups appear relevant for attendees.*

- For the 2025 Summit, the Evaluation team did not observe breakout groups. These were instead observed by the Team Science team and Summit facilitators.
- However, the evaluator observed that in the full group meetings that the research topics and product suggestions were derived from the interests and ideas that applicants and participants in the pre-Summit brainstorming session contributed.
- Participants were also encouraged to modify the topics to better fit their working group’s research interests, product goals and experience.
- The ability of participants to self-select and form their own working groups, encouraged participants to select topics they were personally interested in. The focus on identifying associated products also encouraged participants to think more deeply about the focus and outcomes of their groups’ work.
- During the initial formation of working groups, participants were encouraged and guided to explore multiple potential research topics. Facilitators also emphasized that it was okay to change groups as they assessed their interests during the group formation phase. This also provided attendees with ample opportunities for networking and sharing ideas with multiple participants.

Observation Theme 3: *There is an emphasis on contributions from every participant.*

- The Code of Conduct and the clear commitment of the leadership team to the values of supporting a welcoming atmosphere were introduced on the first day and reiterated throughout the Summit.
- The Discovery Science facilitators led activities to demonstrate the ways in which different people think and process information (e.g., “Positive Polarities” activity) and how this might look within a working group. They discussed the processes involved in divergent and convergent thinking and provided tips on how to include group members’ ideas even if they do not seem immediately relevant.
 - In later share-out sessions, participants shared that they had gained new insights into how their group members may have differing ways of processing and sharing ideas (e.g., internal and external processing) and that this helped them to learn about different workflows.
- Tribal ESIIIL partners gave opening remarks at the beginning of the Summit, and ESIIIL leaders spoke about the importance of embracing multiple knowledge systems in the work to address complex topics in Environmental Data Science. A Tribal ESIIIL community member also provided closing remarks at the end of the Summit, sharing personal experiences with the ESIIIL community and providing reminders of how all community members are connected to each other and the land, and encouraged everyone to consider their impacts as they work with each other to engage in ethical research practices and care for the Earth.

Observation Theme 4: *The summit atmosphere is relaxed, open, friendly, fun and welcoming (including newcomers and those new to EDS).*

- The participants appeared to enjoy engagement in activities like the “Positive Polarities.” However, the evaluator did not speak to them directly about this.

- Materials were provided at the tables for participants to create art or use as fidgets (mostly pipe cleaners of various colors). They were encouraged to share anything they created on the pipe cleaner showcase table. There were several creative contributions on display by the end of the Summit.
- The leadership also offered opportunities to create affinity groups and suggested times to meet with these groups (e.g., at social events).
- Counterfactual Evidence: Small group facilitators were asked to observe when participants might be struggling to engage and invite them in or help summarize their ideas and connect them with other group members' ideas. One of the facilitators pointed out to the evaluator that there were two participants who seemed disengaged on the first day, wanting to work on their own or seen sitting alone, away from the other participants. This facilitator and another small-group facilitator spoke to these participants to make sure they were included and to check in on their needs. The facilitator shared with the evaluator that one participant did not seem interested in joining a working group and wanted to work with someone online who was not present at the conference. It was unclear whether this was influenced by the atmosphere of the conference. The other person they observed responded well to the small group facilitator's guidance and eventually joined a working group.

Observation Theme 5: *Participants learned about useful skills or tools related to EDS or they applied skills and tools.*

- Participants were trained prior to the Summit on how to use Cyverse and Github. During the meeting, the groups used Github to share their proposals and access data sets and other resources.
- The evaluator did not observe breakout group sessions where most of the work using these tools took place.

Observation Theme 6: *There are opportunities for and encouragement of collaborative work and interactive knowledge exchange/transdisciplinary work.*

- This was apparent throughout the meeting. During share-out sessions, some participants shared how the members of their working group contributed in various ways, coming from different backgrounds and experiences. For example:
 - In one group, a participant shared that although they had thought and read a lot about Indigenous Ways of Knowing, they had not actually seen it put into practice in a research collaboration until the Summit. They also expressed a desire to slow down their group's process, especially for members focused on technology, and follow guidance from the Indigenous scholars in the group.
 - A member of another group lightheartedly mentioned that they had run a model incorrectly due to a misunderstanding of a term used differently by data scientists and other scientific disciplines represented in their working group. Through the collaboration, they learned the terminology in a new context.
 - Another group shared that they wanted to invite all of the attendees to participate in a survey they were preparing about improving data management. They noted that they wanted the project to be community-centered for ESIL/EDS researchers so that it would be helpful to this community broadly.

- In a later share-out session, another participant shared that they were amazed at how quickly the research landscape was changing and indicated that diverse perspectives are needed to navigate this.

Observation Theme 7 (Emergent Theme): *Participants identified products associated with their working groups' research topics.*

- The participants were asked to consider their goals for products resulting from their research projects as they identified a research topic and formed their working groups. During share-out sessions, they mentioned a variety of different products they planned to result from the work, including:
 - Papers/Publications (e.g., “Call-to-action” paper; Journal article; Article in the Journal of EDS Special Issue organized by ESIL)
 - Grant Proposal
 - Submit an ESIL Working Group application
 - Workshop/Festival to educate the public
 - Data dashboard
 - LLM to help Indigenous scholars and decision-makers query and use data
- This theme was relevant for the unconference format in that it seemed to help participants choose a working group that was relevant both for their research interests and expertise as well as their goals from resulting products. The Discovery Science facilitators also indicated that sometimes a large group will form around a research topic, but that it can be broken down into smaller collaborations around a specific product.
 - This happened with one of the working groups who initially brought together a large number of people interested in the topic. They identified a need for multiple products to address their overarching question. To accommodate this, they formed three smaller groups with the intention of coming together later to discuss their findings and combine efforts in addressing the overarching research focus. For example, the groups focused on a) developing a community education event; b) creating a Language Learning Model to help Indigenous scholars and decision-makers query the data to address specific questions; and c) create a dashboard where the data could be queried and displayed.

ESIL Culture

The majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the **contributions of all group members were valued (94%)**. Respondents also agreed or strongly agreed that they **felt comfortable providing feedback (95%)** and **contributing opposing viewpoints (83%)** (Figures 12 and 13).

Figure 12

Figure 13

Participants' Perspectives on Being Members of the EDS Community

Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted to evaluate changes in respondents' pre-survey and reflection survey responses about how they identify with being a member of the EDS community. Before and after the Summit, respondents were asked to "choose the picture that best described the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community." Results showed a significant change such **that respondents saw a greater overlap between themselves and the EDS community at the end of the Summit** compared to before the Summit ($Z = 4.29$, $p < 0.001$), (Figure 14).

Figure 14

Respondents were also asked to rate the extent to which they agreed with statements about their sense of belonging in the EDS community. Respondents' **agreement significantly increased from pre- to post-survey** for **"I belong to the EDS Community"** ($Z = 3.63, p < 0.001$) and **"Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity"** ($Z = 2.70, p = 0.007$) (Figure 15).

Figure 15

Summit Overall Highlights

The best parts of the ESIL Innovation Summit, according to respondents, can be summarized into the following key themes:

- **Networking and Community Building:** Respondents valued meeting new people, connecting with like-minded individuals, and expanding their professional networks.
- **Teamwork and Collaboration:** Working on brainstorming ideas and engaging in live collaboration on meaningful projects was highly appreciated for fostering effective teamwork.
- **Welcoming and Supportive Environment:** Many highlighted the welcoming atmosphere and strong support from organizers as key strengths of the Summit.
- **Technical Learning and Resources:** Respondents valued access to technical discussions, tools, and resources that supported their projects.
- **Exposure to Multiple Perspectives:** Respondents appreciated hearing ideas from people with different backgrounds, including indigenous perspectives and interdisciplinary approaches.

Survey respondents recommended the following improvements for future Summits:

Advance Communication and Preparation

- **Early Information Sharing:** Respondents suggested *“letting participants know potential science questions one day in advance”* to give attendees *“time to process what they may be interested in.”*
- **Pre-Summit Group Formation:** Several recommended forming groups earlier to prior to the Summit to allow attendees the *“opportunity to start pulling together data earlier.”*

Group Dynamics and Selection

- **Inclusivity in Participation:** Some noted that *“it’s a little tough for those that have quieter voices to have a chance for input”* or that group work was inefficient due to those who wish not to *“steamroll the conversation.”*
- **Clearer Processes:** Respondents felt the topic selection process was *“a bit chaotic”* and that it was *“it was hard to tell how many people were actually interested in a topic since we shifted posters every few minutes.”* Some also noted that they wished there was *“more flexibility around joining groups.”*
- **Inter-group Engagement:** Respondents suggested that it would be great to engage with other teams since they didn’t *“get to interact much”* with those on other teams.

Time Management

- **Duration Concerns:** Suggestions included indicating that the *“last day could be extended to the afternoon.”* One respondent suggested that *“a second science jam where the goal is to link data to the questions/topics”* could be a way to incorporate more time.
- **Balance Between Activities:** Respondents indicated they wanted more networking opportunities without compromising project time. Some noted that it was *“exhausting being in the room for an entire day”* and then *“asked to go for socials that evening.”*

Expectations and Scope

- **Realistic Goals:** Respondents noted that project expectations *“were too big”* within *“such a short time scale,”* and that the *“Summit could have helped bound the expectations better.”*

Group Support

- **Technical and Focused Work Sessions:** Respondents indicated that they wanted *“more technical training”* and *“breakouts for groups once they are going in a solid direction.”* Others mentioned *“more hands-on with data analysis and digging into relevant datasets for insights.”*
- **Increased Collaboration Time:** Some respondents expressed that the facilitation was *“a bit heavy handed”* and that it *“disrupted the flow of working with teams.”* They suggested that they wished more time was spent *“connecting with the other participants.”*
- **Demonstrations:** Respondents suggested that *“mini-sessions of working group awardees”* can help to demonstrate the *“commitment they needed to produce in order to succeed as a working group”* that resulted in meaningful advancement from participating in the Summit.

In a final open-ended question, respondents were asked to *Please share any other feedback you have about the ESIL Innovation Summit*. Themes and representative verbatim responses are included below. These themes were further categorized as Positive Feedback, indicating aspects of the Summit that participants appreciated or enjoyed and Areas for Improvement, indicating suggestions made to improve the Summit.

Positive Feedback

Overall Experience

- *“Thank you for arranging the summit despite all the hardships. Hope you are continuing to be able to do so.”*
- *“Thank you ESIL staff for being so kind!”*
- *“You are all so great! Thank you for letting me be part of this and having this experience!”*
- *“It was really fun and not as exhausting as some other conferences can be.”*
- *“It was awesome!”*
- *“Highly recommended”*
- *“Thanks!”*
- *“Great job... I definitely hope to come back”*
- *“You are all so great! Thank you for letting me be part of this and having this experience!”*
- *“I appreciated the Divergent Science facilitators! I felt they added a lot of value to the conference and also especially for my breakout group. I also learned a lot from them during the leadership meeting.”*

Learning and Collaboration

- *“As I’ve already shared, I had a fantastic time at the summit making new connections and learning new environmental data science techniques and research topics that has only increased my passion for EDS and interest in participating in an ESIL working group. The inclusive environment that ESIL and Divergent Science team created played a big part in that. Thank you and I’m so grateful for being a part of this ‘s summit!”*
- *“I see solutions that I did not see before the Summit. I see possibilities for collabs I probably would not have encountered without the Summit”*

Suggestions for Future Events

- *“I hope the Summit can keep going through more connections. I think inviting or contacting more TCU students can help more realize what an excellent resource that ESIL provides. In Lakota culture, our elders are the culture bearers. They are usually over 60 years old. The rest of us carry out their wisdom while making sure the youth are ready to help when ready.”*

Areas for Improvement

Group Selection

- *“I wish there was more time to determine where I best fit in groups. While I was interested in the concept of the group I was in, fundamentally, I was much more drawn to the topics of another group that had evolved since it was posted on the sticky sheets. I also didn't feel like standing around a sheet was the best way to interview topics and group members.”*

General Suggestions for Improvement

- *“Thank you! I think Divergent Science did a great job with facilitation, and I think there is room for improvement in terms of reducing expectations and promises. There were a ton of good intentions set forth, but we didn't quite get to follow up with them. I think ESIL is biting of a little more than it can chew with trying to promote good group dynamics, collaborating with Indigenous partners, facilitating interdisciplinary science, and teaching how to use big data tools. However, I believe in dreaming big and I think that ESIL should keep going on this path because it will get easier as more people come to this work. It can be hard to be on the “bleeding edge” of innovation, but keep at it! I hope to stay in touch and continue participating.”*

Summit Outcomes: Overall Impacts and Innovation

A subset of open-ended questions was asked only of the ESIL leadership team, Advisory board members, and Summit breakout group leaders. There were only 2 respondents who elected to answer these questions. Their responses are given verbatim below:

Impacts of the ESIL Innovation Summit Over the Next 6 Months

- *“Our team will write a fantastic proposal. Navigation and onboarding will continually improve.”*
- *“New papers, software, data integrations, grant proposals and other collaboration.”*

Impacts of the ESIL Innovation Summit on Innovation

- *“Conference is key. Calling out ideas as edgy or inciteful helped with reflection.”*
- *“Upskilling community to cloud and AI.”*

Impacts of the ESIL Innovation Summit on a Decadal EDS Research Agenda

Note: only one survey respondent elected to answer this question.

- *“AI prompt engineering a la [redacted/potentially identifying details] will transform the field, particularly as it moves into educational materials and follow ups after summit”*

Impacts of the Summit Toward Advancing the field of EDS

Several themes emerged regarding how the ESIL Innovation Summit advanced the field of EDS.

Representative verbatim responses are included below each theme (N = 29).

Collaboration Across Disciplines and Expertise: Bringing together people from different backgrounds and career stages to work on shared challenges was a key element.

- *“By bringing people together from all over, who probably normally would not interact, and converging them on a topic that they could approach from a number of different perspectives, tools, and ideas.”*
- *“It lived up to the goal of connecting interdisciplinary practitioners across the spectrum of career stages. I felt this facilitated great discussions and allowed us to collaborate with people we otherwise might never have gotten the opportunity to work with.”*

Advancing Environmental Data Science: Increasing awareness and adoption of EDS tools, datasets, and methodologies to improve research practices and standards.

- *“The ESIIIL Innovation Summit brings together novel groups that have the chance to take on new directions and push the field of Environmental Data Science.”*
- *“The Innovation Summit advances EDS by providing opportunities for people who had not previously known about the capabilities, to implement in their studies and/or work. The hands on training helps those who need to hear, watch, and do it, such as us Lakota people.”*

Hands-On Learning and Practical Training: Providing experiential learning opportunities through workshops and demonstrations to make tools and techniques more approachable.

- *“The opportunity to learn new things.”*
- *“By providing training and bringing people together.”*
- *“Fostered sharing of new EDS methods (vibecoding) and ideas (conservation frameworks, causal inference frameworks, etc.)”*

Innovation and Idea Generation: Facilitating brainstorming and creative problem-solving to spark new research directions and collaborative projects.

- *“Created new ideas and matched people to form groups that are both capable and interested in working on projects to attempt answering questions related to the ideas.”*
- *“By bringing people together from such different backgrounds and career stages the Innovation Summit really does fuel innovation. It facilitates thinking and discussion about topics that would be difficult to develop without a space designed specifically for the sharing of ideas and the creation of some product. I also think it lends itself towards discussions about data science as a whole and the future of the field.”*

Introducing New Viewpoints and Tensions: Fostered deeper interdisciplinary engagement by addressing collaboration challenges, normalizing AI practices, and expanding participants' perspectives.

- *“Normalizing discussion about AI at multiple levels, including by modeling in practice.”*
- *“I think it brought up a lot of tensions, specifically around the challenges in interdisciplinary science, including how to figure out how to align different data sets and communicate across various coding languages.”*

Survey Respondents' Takeaways from the Summit

Summit attendees were asked to describe three takeaways they gained from the ESIIIL Innovation Summit. Below are common themes identified among their responses (N = 32):

- **Skill Development in Cyberinfrastructure and AI Tools:** Respondents gained hands-on experience with platforms like CyVerse, GitHub, and cloud computing, as well as practical knowledge of AI-assisted

coding and metadata management. Respondents noted that these skills are helping them build secure, scalable workflows and better understand data structures and interoperability challenges.

- **New Collaborations and Interdisciplinary Networks:** Respondents frequently mentioned forming new collaborations and connecting with experts across disciplines, including RAD management, simulation modeling, and Indigenous knowledge systems. These relationships are expected to foster future research partnerships and enrich their scientific perspectives.
- **Community Building:** Many respondents expressed appreciation for the welcoming and respectful environment of the Summit. This atmosphere fostered a sense of belonging and purpose.
- **Resources and Tools for Research:** Many respondents appreciated access to advanced tools, such as CyVerse and cloud computing facilities, that enhanced their research capabilities. Respondents also discovered new templates, data libraries, that are helping them to structure their projects more effectively and access tools that support long-term data archiving and collaborative research.
- **Improved Data Science and Analytical Methods:** Respondents reported learning new analytical techniques such as geospatial analysis in R, that are enhancing their ability to work with complex datasets and to apply rigorous methods to environmental questions.
- **Personal and Professional Growth:** Many attendees reflected on increased confidence in their scientific identity, improved ability to manage difficult situations, and a clearer vision of the kind of researcher they aspire to be.

Figure 16

Seventy-seven percent of respondents indicated that they were **motivated to continue to work and innovate on ideas related to EDS** after the Summit to a very large or to a large extent (Figure 16).

Reflections on the 2025 ESIL Innovation Summit: Longitudinal Survey Results

[November 2025: These findings will be added to the report after the Longitudinal Survey responses are collected, about 9 months – 1 year after the Summit]

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Appendix A: 2025 ESIL Innovation Summit Agenda

2025 Innovation Summit Agenda

Environmental Tipping Points and Transformations

September 23-25, 2025

SEEC Auditorium, University of Colorado Boulder

<https://cu-esil.github.io/Innovation-Summit-2025/>

Day One - Tuesday, September 23rd

Time	Event	Location
8:30 AM	Registration <i>Light breakfast and snacks available</i>	SEEC Atrium
9:00 AM	Welcome and Land Acknowledgement	SEEC Auditorium
9:05 AM	Opening Ceremony	SEEC Auditorium
9:10 AM	Intentional Innovation	SEEC Auditorium
9:25 AM	Begin with the End in Mind	SEEC Auditorium
9:35 AM	Event Resources Guidelines	SEEC Auditorium
9:45 AM	Positive Polarities	SEEC Auditorium
10:05 AM	Navigating Miscommunications	SEEC Atrium
10:15 AM	Critical Transitions, Uncertainty, and the Quest for Model-Free Decisions Speaker: Carl Boettiger, Associate Professor, University of California, Berkeley	SEEC Atrium
10:30 AM	Group Photo	SEEC Atrium

10:40 AM	Break	SEEC Atrium
10:50 AM	Getting into Groups Part 1	
12:00 PM	Lunch	SEEC Atrium
12:45 PM	Predicting and Managing Ecological Transformations for Climate-Adapted Landscapes Speaker: Katherine Siegel <i>Assistant Professor, University of Colorado Boulder</i>	SEEC Atrium
12:45 PM	Getting into Teams Part 2	
1:45 PM	Science of Team Science <i>What makes great teams?</i>	SEEC Auditorium
2:30 PM	Big Data for Tipping Points	
2:40 PM	Team Breakouts: Innovation Time	Assigned Rooms
3:15 PM	Break	SEEC Atrium
3:30 PM	Team Breakouts: Innovation Time	Assigned Rooms
4:20 PM	Report Back In GitHub	Assigned Rooms
4:50 PM	Whole Group Reflection and Check-in	SEEC Auditorium
4:55 PM	Day 1 Evaluation	SEEC Auditorium
5:00 PM	Day 1 Close	
5:15 - 7:15 PM	Reception at Boulder Social	1600 38th St, Boulder, CO 80301

Day Two - Wednesday, September 24th

Time	Event	Location
8:30 AM	<i>Light breakfast and snacks available</i>	SEEC Atrium
9:00 AM	Welcome Back	SEEC Auditorium
9:10 AM	<p>Using causal inference to detect climate change impacts in ecological systems</p> <p>Speaker: Joan Dudney <i>Assistant Professor, Bren School of Environmental Science & Management, University of California, Santa Barbara</i></p>	SEEC Auditorium
9:25 PM	Prepare for the day	SEEC Auditorium
9:30 AM	Team Breakouts: Innovation Time	Breakout Spaces
11:30 PM	Round 2 Report	
12:00 PM	Lunch	SEEC Atrium Option to Eat Outside
12:45 PM	<p>Working Through the Groan Zone <i>Tips and Tricks to Thrive in the Groan Zone</i></p>	SEEC Auditorium
1:30 PM	Team Breakouts: Innovation Time	Breakout Spaces
4:40 PM	Begin with the End in Mind Part 2	SEEC Auditorium
4:50 PM	Whole Group Reflection	
5:00 PM	Day 2 Close	SEEC Auditorium

Day Three - Thursday, September 25th

Time	Event	Location
8:30 AM	<i>Light breakfast and snacks available</i>	SEEC Atrium
9:00 AM	Welcome Back	SEEC Auditorium
9:05 AM	Final Team Breakout: Prepare for the Final Report Back	Breakout Spaces
10:00 AM	Final Break	SEEC Atrium
10:10 AM	Final Report Out	SEEC Auditorium
11:45 AM	What's Next?	SEEC Auditorium
11:55 AM	Final Reflection	SEEC Auditorium
11:59 AM - Noon	Closing	SEEC Auditorium

Appendix B: Evaluation Surveys

2024 ESIL Summit Pre-Survey

ESIL Innovation Summit participants were selected based on their ability to help build the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community of the future. Understanding the thoughts and opinions of Innovation Summit participants is therefore crucial. Please fill out the information below to the best of your ability.

Please consider the following definition of Environmental Data Science when answering the questions in this survey: *We define EDS broadly to include any work where large data sets are used to drive discovery, solutions, and science to understand our environment. It is highly transdisciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences.*

Please provide your first and last name

How did you learn about the ESIL Innovation Summit? Select all that apply.

- I attended a past ESIL Innovation Summit.
- I participated in an ESIL Hackathon or Coding event.
- I received an email from ESIL@colorado.edu.
- LinkedIn
- Twitter/X
- ESIL's website
- Word of Mouth - I heard from others about it
- An online forum or Slack channel (e.g., ECOLOG, AISES). If so, which one:

- Other:

What would you like to get out of your participation in the ESIL Innovation Summit? Please share **1 - 3 personal goals** you have for the Summit.

We are interested in learning about how your participation in the ESIL Innovation Summit is shaping your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	N/A
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>					
Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>					

What is your primary role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (EDS)? Please select one.

- Director/Program Manager
- Project/Field Manager
- Analyst
- Technician
- Researcher
- Educator (Lecturer/K-12/Informal/Teaching Faculty)
- Student
- Other _____
- Prefer not to answer

Which of the following best describes your current career stage?

- Student (I am an undergraduate student or a graduate student)
- Early Career (I am a post-doctoral fellow, or have 0 to 5 years of professional experience.)
- Mid-Career (I have 6 to 15 years of professional experience.)
- Senior (I have more than 15 years of professional experience.)
- Other. Please describe. _____
- Prefer not to answer

What best describes the organization in which you work?

- Academic (higher education)
- Government: Federal
- Government: State
- Government: Local
- Industry
- K-12 or Informal Education
- Non-profit: Research and Development (FFRDC/National Labs/etc)
- Non-profit: other
- Private for-profit
- Tribal Organization
- Self

Other: _____

Prefer not to answer

Are you affiliated with an academic institution?

Yes

No

Unsure

Display This Question:

If Are you affiliated with an academic institution? = Yes

With which type of academic institution are you affiliated? Select all that apply.

Community College/ 2-yr College

Professional Program

American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institutions (AAPISI)

Hispanic Serving Institution (HSI)

Historically Black University (HBCU)

Tribal College or Tribal-Serving Institution (TCU)

Minority Serving Institution (MSI)

Primarily Undergraduate Serving

Undergraduate and Graduate Serving

Research Intensive (R1/R2/etc)

If none of the options fit, how would you describe the main organization you are affiliated with?

Prefer not to answer

Which of the following categories best describe your highest level of education?

- Some high school
- High school diploma or equivalent
- Vocational training
- Some college
- Associate degree (e.g. AA, AE, AFA, AS, ASN)
- Bachelor's degree (e.g. BA, BBA, BFA, BS)
- Some graduate work
- Master's degree (e.g. MA, MBA, MFA, MS, MSW)
- Applied or professional graduate degree (e.g. MD, DDS, JD)
- Doctoral degree (e.g. EdD, PhD)
- Not listed, please specify: _____
- I prefer not to answer

In what field and in what year did you receive your highest degree?

What are the main professional societies to which you belong? Please select up to 5 professional societies from the drop-down menu, or type in the organization's full name.

Professional Society #1

Professional Society #2

Professional Society #3

Professional Society #4

Professional Society #5

In which disciplinary field(s) of Environmental Data Science do you MAINLY work? Select all that apply.

- Artificial Intelligence/ Machine Learning
- Biological science
- Chemistry/ Biochemistry
- Computer/Data Science
- Economics
- Engineering
- Environmental Science
- Geoscience (Geology, Geography)
- Math
- Social Science
- Other. Please specify. _____
- Prefer not to answer
- I don't work in an EDS field.

Where do you live?

I live in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code:)

I am outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?)

I prefer not to answer

Where is your place of work located?

Place of work is in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code:)

Place of work within a Tribal Nation (If yes, list the Tribal Nation)

Place of work is outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?)

I prefer not to answer

2024 ESIL Summit Reflection Survey

Thank you for joining us for the ESIL Innovation Summit. The ESIL leadership team would like to learn about your experiences at the Summit in order to better understand its impacts on innovation and building a broader Environmental Data Science network. Your feedback will help us to continue to improve future Summits as we build the broader ESD community.

Please provide your first and last name. _____

What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply.

- Participant
- Speaker or Presenter
- Facilitator
- ESIL advisory board member
- Technical helper or Logistics Support
- ESIL partner
- ESIL leadership team
- Other (Please Specify) _____

In which Pre-Summit Activities did you engage? Please select all that apply.

- Science Jam: Creative Brainstorming to Inspire Innovation (August 5th, 2025)
- Navigating CyVerse and Github: A Gateway to Advanced Computation for Science (September 3rd, 2025)
- Creative Data Exploration in the Cloud with AI: Innovating with Open Science (September 9th, 2025)
- Leadership Training (September 22nd, 2025)
- I did not attend the pre-Summit activities

Display This Question:

If In which Pre-Summit Activities did you engage? Please select all that apply. != I did not attend the pre-Summit activities

To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following components of the Pre-Summit trainings and activities prepared you for the Summit? (Select N/A if you did not participate in a component)

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
“Science Jam: Brainstorming	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Navigating Cyverse and Github	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cloud Computing basics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cloud Computing with AI	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaborating with others on Cloud Computing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Leadership Skills	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Recommended Reading List	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Display This Question:

If In which Pre-Summit Activities did you engage? Please select all that apply. != I did not attend the pre-Summit activities

In what ways could the pre-Summit sessions be improved?

Overall, how satisfied were you with the ESIIIL Innovation Summit?

- Very Satisfied
- Moderately Satisfied
- Neutral
- Moderately Dissatisfied
- Very Dissatisfied

What were the best parts of the ESIIIL Innovation Summit?

How could the ESIIIL Innovation Summit be improved?

To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following parts of the ESIIIL Innovator Summit were effective?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Positive Polarities Icebreaker activity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Speakers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout group time	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Balance of participation (active/passive learning)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social Activities (e.g., informal social mixer)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Whole Group/Community Discussions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reflections and Reporting Back	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaborating with others on Cloud Computing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Identifying products associated with your research topic	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
The goals of sessions were clearly communicated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The meeting was well-facilitated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online resources were useful	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Speakers and presenters were engaging	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The unconference format worked well	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were plenty of networking opportunities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Food provided was good	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Interactive communication through Slack was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The ESIL Innovation Summit followed an Unconference Format. Please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree that the following characteristics of this format were implemented successfully.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
The breakout group topics were relevant to attendees.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were opportunities for participants to directly influence what was happening each day at the Summit.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There was an emphasis on welcoming the contributions of every participant.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Facilitation of the Summit was inclusive and welcoming of all ideas regardless of background experience (i.e., no idea is too trivial)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The atmosphere of the Summit was relaxed, open, friendly and fun.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The atmosphere of the Summit was welcoming for newcomers and those new to EDS.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were adequate opportunities to network with people of shared interests in EDS	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participants learned about and/or applied useful skills or tools related to EDS.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were opportunities for collaborative, transdisciplinary work and exchange of ideas.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The statements below focus on how the technical support and cyberinfrastructure was helpful for your success at the Summit. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with each statement.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I gained a broader understanding of data science	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I gained a broader understanding of cyberinfrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I learned about new opportunities for the synthesis of data in my field	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I learned about a new technology or techniques that I can apply in my research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent did data and computing infrastructure facilitate the use of AI/ML in your group proposal?

- To a Large Extent
- To a Moderate extent
- To a Small Extent
- To a Very Small Extent
- Not Applicable

Thinking about the ESIIIL **Innovation Summit overall**, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Colleagues showed a general respect for one another	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Colleagues respected the expertise of others in the group	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The contributions of all group members were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Disagreements were handled constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The meeting code of conduct was consistently implemented	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thinking about **your own experiences** during the meeting, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I felt respected by my colleagues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Others in my group respected my expertise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt my contributions were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I handled disagreements constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
Breakout groups gathered a group of enthusiastic collaborators	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout group brainstorming was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout groups developed initial plans for projects	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout groups created an outline for a project	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Breakout groups developed a plan to collaborate beyond the Summit	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Plans for the future breakout group collaboration seem feasible	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent are you motivated to continue to work and innovate on ideas related to EDS?

- To a Very Large Extent
- To a Large Extent
- To a Moderate Extent
- To a Small Extent
- To a Very Small Extent

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	N/A
AI tools were useful for my Summit working group.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The use of AI tools increased tension in my Summit working group.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have a more positive view of the utility of AI tools in my work after participating in the ESIIIL Summit	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I intend to continue using AI/ML in my work after the Summit.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please provide any other feedback you have on the breakout groups.

Display This Question:

If What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = Facilitator or Breakout Group leader

Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL leadership team

Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL advisory board member

What impacts do you anticipate the ESIL Innovation Summit will have over the next 6 months?

Display This Question:

If What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = Facilitator or Breakout Group leader

Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL leadership team

Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL advisory board member

In which ways, if at all, do you think the ESIL Innovation Summit will lead to innovation?

Display This Question:

If What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = Facilitator or Breakout Group leader

Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL leadership team

Or What best describes your role at the Innovation Summit? Select all that apply. = ESIL advisory board member

In which ways, if at all, do you think the ESIL Innovation Summit will shape a decadal research agenda of EDS?

In which ways do you think the ESIL Innovation Summit advanced the field of Environmental Data Science?

Please describe up to three new things that you will take away from the ESIL Innovation Summit (e.g., skills, ideas, contacts, other resources, etc.).

How many new connections or research collaborations have you made during the Summit?

- 1 to 3
- 4 to 6
- 7 to 9
- 10 or more
- I did not make any new connections or research collaborations.

We are interested in learning about how your participation in the ESIL Innovation Summit has shaped your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of an Environmental Data Science (EDS) professional after having participated in the ESIL Innovation Summit.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>				
Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>				

Please share any other feedback you have about the ESIL Innovation Summit.
